

**SOME LIMIT THEOREMS FOR THE CRITICAL GALTON-WATSON
BRANCHING PROCESSES**

Kudratov Kh.¹, Saydulloyeva Sh.²

¹Samarkand State University, 15, University street, Uzbekistan,
qudratovh-83@mail.ru;

²Samarkand State University, 15, University street, Uzbekistan,
saydulloyevash1996@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6645818>

Suppose that $\{\xi(k, j), k, j \in \mathbb{N}\}$ be a sequence of independent identically distributed random variables taking non-negative integer values. Let the random variable $\xi(1, 1)$ have the distribution

$$p_k = P(\xi(1, 1) = k), k = 0, 1, \dots,$$

with the generating function

$$F(s) := E s^{\xi(1,1)} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} p_k s^k, 0 \leq s \leq 1,$$

and $p_0 + p_1 \neq 1$. Consider the process $W(k), k \geq 0$ defined by the following recurrent relation:

$$W(0) = \eta, \quad W(n) = \sum_{j=1}^{W(n-1)} \xi(n, j), n \in \mathbb{N}, \quad (1)$$

here η is a random variable that takes positive integer values and independent on the sequence of random variables $\{\xi(k, j), k, j \in \mathbb{N}\}$.

We call the process $\{W(k), k \geq 0\}$ the Galton-Watson process starting with a random number of particles η . It is well known [1], the asymptotic state of the process $\{W(k), k \geq 0\}$ depends on the mean value of the random variable $\xi(1, 1)$, and it is divided into the classes as follows. It is clear that $F'(1) = E\xi(1, 1)$. The process (1) is called subcritical, critical and supercritical if $F'(1) < 1$, $F'(1) = 1$ and $F'(1) > 1$, respectively.

In this work, we consider only critical processes.

We denote the Galton-Watson process generated by the i -th particle in the initial state by $W_i(n), n = 0, 1, \dots$. Obviously, $W_i(n), n = 0, 1, \dots, i \geq 1$ form independent and identically distributed Galton-Watson branching processes. It is known [1] that $W(n)$ can be represented as

$$W(n) = \sum_{i=1}^{\eta} W_i(n), n \in \mathbb{N} \quad (2)$$

Independence of random variables η and $\xi(i, j), i \geq 1, j \geq 1$ implies independence of $W_i(n)$ and the random variable η . Denote by $P(n)$ the probability of degeneration of the process $\{W(k), k \geq 0\}$ at the n -th step, i.e.

$P(n) = P(W(n) = 0)$. We denote by $R(n)$ the probability of continuation of the process $W_1(n)$ at the n -th step, i.e. $R(n) = P(W_1(n) > 0)$. In what follows, we need the following designations:

$Q(n) = 1 - P(n)$, $h(s) := Es^n$, $H_n(s) := Es^{W(n)}$, $A = h'(1)$, $\sigma^2 = F''(1)$, $F_0(s) = s$, $F_1(s) = F(s)$, $F_n(s) = F(F_{n-1}(s))$ is the n -th iteration of $F(s)$.

Further the sign $a_n \sim b_n$ indicates that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a_n}{b_n} = 1$.

The case when the process $\{W(k), k \geq 0\}$ starts with one particle ($\eta = 1$) has been studied by many authors. So, in 1938, A.N. Kolmogorov [2] obtained the following famous result for the probability of continuation $R(n)$ of the critical Galton-Watson process:

$$R(n) \sim \frac{2}{\sigma^2 n}. \quad (3)$$

In 1947, A.M. Yaglom [3] studied the conditional distribution of the variable $W(n)$ given $W(n) > 0$ and obtained the following result:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P\left(\frac{2}{\sigma^2 n} W(n) \leq y / W(n) > 0\right) = 1 - e^{-y}, \quad y > 0, \quad (4)$$

here it was required $F'''(1) < \infty$. The given results (3), (4) were later obtained by Kesten, Ney, Spitzer [4] under the condition $F''(1) < \infty$. In [5], V.M. Zolotarev obtained similar results for branching processes with continuous parameters.

In 1968, Slack [6] considered the case of

$$F(s) = s + (1 - s)^{1+\alpha} L(1 - s), \quad \alpha \in (0, 1], \quad (S)$$

here $L(x)$ is a slowly varying function on a neighborhood of zero, and obtained the following:

$$(1 - F_n(0))^\alpha L(1 - F_n(0)) \sim \frac{1}{\alpha n}, \quad (5)$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E(\exp\{-\lambda(1 - F_n(0))W(n)\} / W(n) > 0) = 1 - \lambda(1 + \lambda^\alpha)^{-1/\alpha}, \quad \lambda > 0. \quad (6)$$

This result implies the result by Yaglom (4) if $\alpha \equiv 1$ and $F''(1) < \infty$. It should be noted that in the case considered by Slack, the equality $F''(1) = \infty$ can be satisfied. Theorem 1. If condition (S) is satisfied and $h''(1) < \infty$, then

$$Q^\alpha(n) L(1 - F_n(0)) \sim \frac{A^\alpha}{\alpha n}$$

as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Theorem 2. If (S) holds then

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E(\exp\{-\lambda(1 - H_n(0))W(n)\} / W(n) > 0) = 1 - A\lambda(1 + (A\lambda)^\alpha)^{-1/\alpha}, \quad \lambda > 0$$

In the case of $\eta = 1$, the equality $A = 1$ holds, and in this case Theorem 2 turns of the Slack theorem.

Использованная литература:

1. Harris T.E. The theory of branching processes. Springer - Verlag, Berlin-GöttingenHeidelberg, 1963. 355p.
2. Kolmogorov A.N. K resheniyu odnoy biologicheskoy zadachi// Izv. NII mat. i mex.Tomskogo Universiteta , 1938, t. 2, vip. 1.(in Russian)
3. Yaglom A. M. Nekotore predelnie teoremi teorii vetvyashchixsya sluchaynix protsessov//DAN SSSR, 1947, 56, 8, 795-798.(in Russian)
4. F. Spitzer., H. Kesten., P. Ney. The Galton-Watson process with mean one and finitevariance// Theory of Probability and its Applications, 1966, 11:4, 513-540.
5. Zolotarev V.M. More exact statements of several theorems in the theory of branchingprocesses// Theory of Probability and its Applications, 1957, 2:2, 245-253.
6. Slack R.S. A Branching Process with Mean One and Possibly Infinite Variance// Z. Wahrsch. Verw. Gebiete. 9, 139-145 (1968).